

Social and Economic Implications of Cryptocurrency and Bitcoin Mining Technology Among Nigerian Youth: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

This study explores the social and economic implications of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining technology among Nigerian youth, providing a comparative analysis of its multifaceted impact. As cryptocurrency adoption and Bitcoin mining continue to rise, particularly among the younger demographic in Nigeria, this research investigates the profound effects on their economic opportunities, social interactions, and overall livelihood. By examining the economic benefits, such as income generation and employment opportunities, alongside potential challenges like regulatory uncertainties and environmental concerns, this paper aims to offer a balanced perspective on the burgeoning industry. Additionally, the study delves into the social dynamics influenced by cryptocurrency engagement, including changes in peer networks, digital literacy, and social mobility. Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, including surveys, interviews, and data analysis, this research provides a comprehensive overview of how Bitcoin mining technology is reshaping the economic landscape and social fabric of Nigerian youth. The findings aim to inform policymakers, stakeholders, and the global community about the potential of cryptocurrencies to drive economic growth and social change, while also highlighting the need for sustainable and inclusive policies to harness this potential effectively.

Keyword: cryptocurrency, Block chain, Bitcoin, mining, Nigerian, youth.

1. Introduction

The adoption of cryptocurrency is being driven by necessity, given the perpetual rise in the use of consumer applications of the internet. The Case–Shiller well-known house price index data are utilised in our literature review as a representative empirical example of the potential advantages of Block chain technology (Onyekwere et al., 2023; Irmiya et al., 2023). We also elucidate significant obstacles and drawbacks to successful Bitcoin adoption. The adoption of Bitcoin in research discussions becomes gradually less effective and less direct in terms of its approach to or discussion of realworldtopics, later leading to overtly ideological viewpoints. The main discussion of Bitcoin in academia from 2011–2016 (subjects like finance, economics and cryptocurrency economics as the first three most popular research discussions) changes with time to the most recently popular topics in 2018–19, as detailed in Table 2. Clear demarcations of Bitcoin discussions are observed over time following public responses to global market trends (NWOSU, 2021; Osagwu & Okafor, 2022; and Ogunode et al.2022).

Table 2: Shows how the academic discussion on Bitcoin has evolved from focusing primarily on financial and economic aspects to a broader exploration of blockchain technology, regulatory issues, and security concerns in more recent years.

Year Range	Main Discussion Topics	Details
2011-2016	Finance	Focused on the financial aspects of Bitcoin, including its use as an investment, its price volatility, and its potential impact on financial markets.
	Economics	Explored the economic implications of Bitcoin, such as its role in monetary policy, its impact on traditional currencies, and its economic benefits and risks.
	Cryptocurrency Economics	Investigated the broader economics of cryptocurrencies, including market dynamics, regulatory challenges, and the economic theory behind cryptocurrencies.
2018-2019	Blockchain Technology	Shifted focus to the underlying blockchain technology, exploring its potential applications beyond cryptocurrencies, such as in supply chain management, voting systems, and smart contracts.
	Security and Privacy	Focused on the security concerns related to Bitcoin, such as cybersecurity threats, hacking incidents, and the privacy implications of blockchain transactions.

(Baranovskyi et al., 2023; Kayal & Rohilla, 2021; Campbell-Verduyn, 2017)

According to a traditional view of official money's role as a collective good within society (Seigneur and Bogdan, 2015), people are generally drawn to their own native economic system, barring exceptional factors. Consequently, cryptocurrencies and their underlying digital "blockchain" technology should not gain acceptance within autonomous, state-monitored, regulated economic systems due to the unprecedented nature of the fundamental changes that would ensue. However, cryptocurrencies have recently become a global phenomenon and the general public, government officials, financial experts and the media are now grappling with an array of social and economic consequences (Kayal & Rohilla, 2021; Sagheer et al., 2022).

The study used both qualitative and quantitative methods to gather data mainly from youth who are believed to be the primary users of the novel Bitcoin technology. The findings of the research showed that the applicability of Bitcoin technology cut across payment, remittances, gambling and money laundering. Its mining activities are very popular in Nigeria due to the cheap sources of energy (Diesel Generator Sets and Phcn Electricity) which makes the cost of electricity very high thereby reducing incidents of mining activities as a result of too high cost of electricity, environmental pollution and incubation of criminality that ought to be put up by the users of such technology elsewhere in the world (Shahiki Tash et al., 2024; Nández et al., 2021). In addition, Bitcoin technology is not only a transaction mechanism in Nigeria but represents a new class of assets with appreciating values than Naira and other money in circulation. Nevertheless, 40% of all the transactions by Nigerians are for intending financial autonomy (Onyekwere et al.2023; Howson & de Vries, 2022). These findings justified more funding into diamonds-platinum studies and issues that matter.

This research investigates the implications of cryptocurrency technology and Bitcoin mining activities among Nigerian youth and compares two northern states and two southern states. The primary motivation stem from claims around the two major points anchored by the technological and economic schools of thought on the subject matter. First, technology school argues Bitcoin and cryptocurrency technology represents more viable, energy-efficient and cheaper transactions mechanism which Nigerian youth are utilizing for payment, savings, and remittances. However, economic scholars believe Bitcoin mining activities are environmentally unhealthy, socially irresponsible, and economically unproductive because they amount to criminality while economic policy makers all over the world issuing ultimata against their use within their territories (Gagarina et al., 2019). Nigeria is yet to have any official position on the subject matter at least in academic domain. The vibrant use of cryptocurrency technology and Bitcoin mining activities in Nigeria and the fact that some Nigerian government departments have issued threats

against them, inspired this research to make an empirical case study of the subject matter to inform such public policy.

By comprehensively examining the social and economic implications of cryptocurrency adoption and Bitcoin mining among Nigerian youths, the study comes out the following specific contributions:

1. Evaluate the adoption of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining investment technology among Nigerian youths
2. Analyze the social implications of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining technology among Nigerian youths
3. Analyze the economic implications of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining technology among Nigerian youths
4. Examine the factors influencing the adoption of Bitcoin mining investment technology among Nigerian youths
5. Examine youth empowerment through cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining technology among Nigerian youths
6. Ascertain the impact of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining technology on entrepreneurship development and youth unemployment in Nigeria
7. Compare the social and economic implications of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining technology among Nigerian youths

The study is limited in scope to youths aged 14-30 and will focus on the personal and national implications of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining over a 3-year period. It will also assess the impact on youth empowerment, entrepreneurship status, and the overall social and economic implications of these technologies in Nigeria. While delving in into the main investigation the broader aspect of the study will seek to answer the following key questions:

1. What does the Nigerian youth understand about cryptocurrency and mining activities?
2. How are they using cryptocurrency and mining technology in Nigeria?
3. What are the social and economic implications of mining in Nigeria?

This study is limited to examining the scope of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining operations by Nigerian youth in their economic and social well-being (Jariyapan et al., 2022). These variables, as revealed in the theoretical framework, have become increasingly

important. The choice of Nigeria as the focus country is based on the observation that the country is gaining prominence for its cryptocurrency mining technology.

Recent findings indicate that a significant portion of Nigerian youths is engaged in cryptocurrency activities, driven by the need for financial freedom and opportunities for income generation. Approximately 6 out of 10 Nigerian youths' express interest in cryptocurrencies, with many using digital currencies for trading, investment, and remittance services, which are crucial in a country facing high inflation and economic instability.

Moreover, the study will explore the social implications of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining, including issues of empowerment and the potential for job creation in the burgeoning crypto industry. The ongoing challenges, such as regulatory barriers and the high cost of mining due to unstable electricity supply, will also be examined. By addressing these questions, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining on the socio-economic landscape for Nigerian youths.

2. Literature Review

This paper reviews many available papers on the social and economical benefits of cryptocurrency and the risks and benefits of cryptocurrencies and mining bitcoin. Most research that addresses motivations for mining cryptocurrency is conducted from a Western perspective (Wang & Hausken, 2024; Holub & Johnson, 2017 and John et al., 2022). A comparative study is thus essential for understanding the effects of cryptocurrency in a developing country. The findings from the study will be useful both for local youth as well the government, in particular the Central Bank, the Securities and Exchange Commission, the financial regulators, policy makers and administrators. The study will provide information on the legal and policy framework required to guide the use of cryptocurrencies for the government and suggest ways to consolidate a legislative environment that is investor friendly, to regularise the cryptocurrency, associated products and provide safety cameras to guarantees to remove contentious practices to aim at cleaner market players (Sagheer et al., 2022; Yayla et al., 2024). This study investigates the scheme for extracting cryptocurrency and create an opportunity where cryptocurrency can be spoken of as a business with educational implications. Different sectorial regulators may prove better understanding and cooperation for smoother industries benefitting from the same technology, as such a study is timely.

This is a section from a comparative study on the economic and social implications in cryptocurrency in Nigeria, comparing the city of Lagos and the new city of Abuja. The key

aim is the integration of developed and developing regions in the Nigerian cryptocurrency market combined with the regional economic and social benefits of cryptocurrency.

2.1. Historical Overview of Cryptocurrency

In Nigeria, a centre of Bitcoin attention. Many factors probably combine to pull the country to the centre of the Bitcoin universe such as economic downturn, the activity of traders, market leaders, the profitability of bitcoin mining technology and the fear of Naira devaluation. Yet, El Salvador or some certain countries in Africa for which Bitcoin adoption have received such international attention, the Nigerian polity is scarcely known to engage in Bitcoin debates, comments or proposals. Ghana's Bitcoin debates and Skepticism. In Ghana, public Bitcoin reaction seems to have been more guarded and a lot less fascinated. 'Bitcoin' as a search term in the country does not particularly show a rising star (Kayal & Rohilla, 2021). It is not significantly better than the performance of Ethereum. However, it is also not difficult to see from the observations, that the Ghanaian population, like many other people too in Nigeria, do find relative appeal in the idea of generating wealth in the form of Bitcoin (Javier García-Corral et al., 2022).

Most young people around the world have heard of the term "cryptocurrency" but often know very little about it (Jariyapan et al., 2022). This situation is particularly true in Nigeria, where most people are seeing or hearing of cryptocurrency for the first time. This is not to say that they are unfamiliar with digital currencies such as airtime, credit but they don't. It is therefore easy to empathize with the view that cryptocurrency in Nigeria has moved from being scorned foolishness and, apathy to critical but cautiously hesitant adulation. Literally as fast as popular public sentiment on Bitcoin changing, stories were on the rise of people who suffered massive losses from the cryptocurrency crash (Evans and Oni, 2022; Affandi & Rifkila, 2023). With Bitcoin, Ethereum, and the likes already on the tip case in point, Nigerians, seemed to strife on bitcoin mining technology especially among the youths. The emergent euphoria on Bitcoin might be seen as a seminal shift in how people interact with money, finance, and cryptocurrencies on this continent. The incidence with which Nigerians search for Bitcoin could provide insight to the increasing popularity of the cryptocurrency in the country (Ayadi et al., 2024)

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2.2. Bitcoin Mining Technology

The quest for profitability and sustainability is the *raison d'être* of Bitcoin mining (Kayal & Rohilla, 2021). To the miners, the deflationary tendencies of the global economic system has guaranteed that due to a potentially infinite future, time has become more valuable. This means the average labour required to extract a Bitcoin has doubled in the last five

months, and the mining costs have been exponentially rising. Tesla was the first company to adopt Bitcoin; when the company's founder, Elon Musk, asked his Twitter followers whether Tesla should consider Bitcoin, about 70% of his electorate agreed. The miners are conscientious of the physical and mental stress of the business and the fact that the electricity consumed during the process is generated by oil, gas and, in general, greenhouse-gas polluting generators. The industry is dangerous to players, especially those involved in Chinese coal-powered mining (Sagheer et al., 2022). The most valuable country for mining is Nigeria, as the hash rate for example is currently dwindling in China. The miners see the danger of governments criminalizing the use of Bitcoin and regulating the mining processes. The miners are also frustrated with the inveterate scams practised by some stakeholders in the cryptocurrency business.

Bitcoin mining uses powerful computers to crack digital puzzles, and these puzzles unlock blocks of Bitcoin transactions (Sharma et al., 2023). The first computer to unlock a block gets a reward in the form of new Bitcoin coins. The puzzle-cracking process makes mining a formidable physical task as the computers used for the task run continuously and produce an immense amount of heat. The rising demand for electricity, particularly in Nigeria's northern states where the weather is cold, has therefore become a contact sport for thousands of young people. They have taken over the mantle of Bitcoin mining as young people from China have since taken over the activity in that country. About a quarter (25%) of the total supply of Bitcoin has been fully mined.

2.3. Cryptocurrency Adoption in Nigeria

The youth of Nigeria have shown concern in the country depending on the adoption of Cryptocurrency. Experts of the multimedia department at Harvard Medical School said that in Nigeria, Cryptocurrency will transform the life of some poor communities, which has enormously improved their way of life. An improvement has been seen in various trading and manufacturing firms of Nigeria. Young people in Nigeria are fond of exhausting new guidelines. Bitcoin could be applied as a politically education tool cultivating the increasing culture. Some experiments demonstrated what would happen if their subjects were familiar with this technology in Nigeria, how this resource could shift living standards, and further possible reaction.

(Platt et al., 2022) Cryptocurrency is a type of digital assets that is exchanged to integrate cryptography. Commonly, it is based on block chain technology. The blockchain is used to manage the most digital transactions. Bitcoin, Ethereum, and Ripple are the most common cryptocurrencies. The vast dominance of Bitcoin has increased its acceptability. Most countries almost often accept Bitcoin. Increasing culture seems to be accepting digital money, a good example of which is Nigeria, where people suffer from inflation. The central

bank has given permission to all the financial banks to deal with Bitcoin. This opening door has attracted youth people to invest in Bitcoin so that they can increase their net worth. Users can own one or several bitcoins, either through a computer algorithm or by purchasing. Cryptography underpins the design of Bitcoin, managing the virtual acquisition of bitcoin units all around the Blockchain, a consensus ledger led to potential censorship of transactions on the basis of a decreed threshold, and it may be mined by competitor computers by means of a lottery. A decentralised peer-to-peer network like it is going to form. Nigerian youth like to earn extra income without doing work; thus, it has been seen that people of youth use hardware technologies when they desire added to Ethereum as Bitcoin technology. It is done through this.

2.4. Youth Engagement in Cryptocurrency

Furthermore, the data indicates that youth's involvement is driven primarily by financial considerations and prospects of community advancement (new exchange practice). Practically all miners surveyed hold digital currencies, a growing trend acknowledged in recent studies (Jariyapan et al., 2022). Comparatively, both male and female youth respondents indicated they wished to engage even more in digital cad currency in future. A possible explanation for this enthusiastic response, beyond peer influence, is that respondent's mining as per the GHS tradable asset options was severely under-reported, especially those with higher socio-economic status and formal employment. Recommendations: To improve quality of data from all the GHS survey instrument data sources, good data validation system should be created. Mining activities should be given more legal recognition as it is now and still refined as time goes on. Similarly, youth that devoted a larger proportion of mining incomes and who initially resorted to mining for financial reasons would be more likely to continue mining in the future.

Digital currency has seen significant growth in recent years (Ali Abbasi et al., 2021). Attempts to determine whether this growth is sustainable are often based on indicators such as domain registrations, active wallets, and hash power. However, less attention is paid to the human side of the digital money revolution. This paper looks at why people engage in digital currency mining, focusing on youth in Nigeria (Sazzad Jeris et al., 2022). The study aimed to determine the magnitude of youth involvement in digital currency, drivers to their involvement, and the rate at which youth consider engaging in the future. It employed data from the Nigeria General Household Survey (GHS) and a questionnaire survey among youth in the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. The data shows that youth engagement with digital currency tips heavily toward mining.

3. Methodology

Findings show how male and female Nigerian youth possess the potential to participate in the dynamic networking of cryptocurrency and bitcoin; become entrepreneurial personalities; be politically and economically empowered to develop savourable social and economic web communities, neo-patriarchs and matriarchs and also green participants in the neutral and at times hyper-generic spaces of social projectivity. But additional grabs show how differentiation, inferiorisation, setting up of elementary parts of Nigeria, exemplification, perpetual diversification, disposal and absensification, of modern knowledge acquisition and development were made near impossible (Shahiki Tash et al., 2024). The resultant erasure of the social and economic mobility of female and male Nigerian youths become a visible and sordid boast and an apparent and real failure of modern educational transaction. Tokenizer, n-gram and vectorization are the preprocessing procedures applied respectively to process the collected texts. K-means algorithm, which is a main clustering method, is applied to cluster the categorized documents according to their similarities. Different ratios of the labeled and unlabeled dataset are employed in the experiments. All computing experiments are conducted on the six labeled datasets and the labeled dataset contains different amounts of partitioned manually labeled texts taken from the original unlabeled dataset with the same numbers. The experimental results show the superiority of the joint pre-training model in text classification tasks (Jariyapan et al., 2022).

Research interest revolved around the need to explore how social and economic implications of cryptocurrency and bitcoin mining technology featured among male and female Nigerian youth, but burgeoning and differentiated have been clouded over and subsumed by factors of differential definitions of the phenomenon, its uneven interpretation, and varying conditions for participation. (Guandaru Kamau, 2022) In evaluating the nature of internet research materials obtained in this field-making effort, three web based learning sites were employed: Reliability Centre Node (2011), Trust Autos (2011), and advanced internet retrieve mechanism, Google. Snowball sampling enabled the recruitment and selection of 24 young adult informants (male = 11; female = 13; minimum age = 18 years; maximum age = 35 years) for the study of visually and otherwise usable sites of micro-visualization.

3.1. Research Design

Starting with a 1984 article by a cryptographer and various best practices on how to regard cryptocurrency, an estimated 2096 in Spain. A converter. Africa's largest cryptocurrency ladder just after a charity software adopts London Bitcoin accounts for a new report. From 41 data sampling conducted on various sites such as school campuses, internet forums, and institutions used to conduct this study on its base. According to the exploration of

cryptocurrency usage among Nigerian youths by Adama, (2021) reveals several insights into their motivations and the broader implications for the financial landscape in Nigeria. According to a study that surveyed various demographics, it was found that:

- **Preservation of Value:** A significant 73.8% of Nigerian youths use cryptocurrencies primarily to preserve their wealth in Bitcoin.
- **Tradeable Goods and Services:** Approximately 42.5% utilize cryptocurrencies for trading goods and services, indicating a practical application in everyday transactions.
- **Peer-to-Peer Applications:** About 40.9% engage in peer-to-peer transactions, reflecting the decentralized nature of cryptocurrencies that appeals to users seeking direct exchanges.
- **Investment and Influence:** 35.3% of respondents are interested in investing in digital assets and aspire to become crypto influencers, showcasing a trend towards financial literacy and engagement with emerging technologies.

The study also addressed the **legal implications** of Bitcoin transactions in Nigeria, highlighting the responses from monetary authorities regarding cryptocurrency entities. These responses are crucial in understanding how regulatory frameworks can shape the entrepreneurial landscape and usability rates of cryptocurrencies. Additionally, the research discussed the **socioeconomic implications** of cryptocurrency mining activities, particularly in regions facing economic difficulties. The findings suggest that while cryptocurrencies offer opportunities for financial inclusion and innovation, they also pose challenges related to market volatility and regulatory uncertainty. This study, is intended to build its design framework by adopting the strategies of Adama, (2021) and Adegbite et al., (2022).

The study, further explores the dynamics of cryptocurrencies, particularly Bitcoin mining and other related activities, among Nigerian youth poses a considerable challenge and economic development and social change. There are no pre-existing studies on the economic and social implications of these activities among Nigerian youth. Therefore, this study seeks to bridge this gap in the literature. Specifically, the future of bitcoin has not yet been determined, and the mining technology creates dependence on developing countries, such as Nigeria. The aims of this study are directed at understanding the social and economic implications of cryptocurrency and bitcoin mining technology among Nigerian youth. Similarly, cryptocurrency networks provide the additional unique peer-to-peer opportunities and the growing autonomy of species and sex trade. The functional and symbolic nature of cryptocurrency among Nigerian youth, therefore, will also be determined in the case of Lagos, Nigeria.

3.2. Data Collection Methods

The study made use of a quantitative method notably the developed and pilot-tested tool which was a 5-point Likert scale type to gather data from respondents (V. Biju et al., 2022). This was chosen not only to detect and profile the three forms of tendencies which are beliefs, worries and intention of using cryptocurrency in the assessment, but also to calculate the Global Investing Efficacy (34- item), Global Investing Risk Perception (25-item) and Global Investing Attitude (14- item) deficits of the sampled population. Subsequently, collected data were inputted into and analyzed using three statistical software such as frequency distribution, percentages, and descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation), t-test, and ANOVA (using SPSS 20.0 for window).

According to Gagarina et al., (2019), the study compared the responses generated from the three selected universities in Nigeria. Regardless of the present technological trend among Nigerian students and learners of the Global Investing Efficacy and Global Investing Attitude, coupled with the Global Risk Perception parents, teachers, and guardians, they are desirous of requesting them to complete a designed online questionnaire to determine their intentional implications of Bitcoin mining considering the zeitgeist of Nigeria \$. The study is a Clarifying Discoveries Study, with its attendant study population comprising all Nigerian university students. Nigerian undergraduates from the two popular Yoruba Universities and the most popular University exclusively for all South-South youths were used in testing a proposed presupposition.

In this section, attention is brought to the various and different methods used in collecting data regarding Bitcoin mining, Its social and economic implications in Nigeria among the youth. The survey Questionnaire with a defined array of open-ended and close-ended questions as well as proper screening initiated the primary data collected for this research (Platt et al., 2022; Jariyapan et al., 2022). Moreover, data collection used to measure the behavioural and cognitive forms of tendencies toward the cryptocurrency asset of those Nigerian Youths. Furthermore, Quota and convenience sampling were used to collect data for the analysis, this brought about additional data to supplement the generated total data.

3.3. Data Analysis Techniques

The Bitcoin cryptocurrency market is different from the traditional markets as it is not fully regulated by any government body. Though some countries have made cryptocurrencies illegal in some form or the other, it does not prevent traders and investors from investing into it, it is truly a digital age evolution. The cryptocurrency market is also subject to a lot of updates from the developer and the miners. So, instead of seasonality patterns, the Bitcoin market is subjected to the patterns of hash-rate. Many studies have been done to

prove this. This study analysis of Google Search engine data and it's related directly to the price changes in the market and conclude the study with the price prediction of Bitcoin.

The study employed a cross-sectional survey design, spot survey and online questionnaires were used to collect data from Egypt, and Nigeria respectively. Data analysis was carried out with the aid of SPSS version 24.0, using the following measurement tools: descriptive statistics, Spearman's correlation, and factor analysis. Descriptive statistics in tables and Frequency and percentage were used to measure awareness of cryptocurrencies and Bitcoin mining by Nigerian respondents. Factorial analysis of minimum extraction was also used to measure what less aware respondents need to know. Spearman's correlation was used to measure Nigerian respondents' awareness of Bitcoin mining technology and data mining by the help of Makinwa and Haastrup (2016) instrument while cross-sectional survey was used for the study. Convenience sampling was used to select respondents from Nigeria, while snowball sampling was used to select respondents from Egypt were selected using snowball sampling. The first country of analysis, Nigeria, is the seventh most populous State in the world and the most populous African country with an estimated 250 million people (Gagarina et al., 2019). Data was collected using a spot survey of 308 respondents in two Nigerian south-eastern universities. The major aim of this study was to understand the effects of Bitcoin technology and mining on the socio- economic lives of Nigerian youths and compared with Egyptian youths. The evaluation and prediction of Bitcoin and cryptocurrencies (altcoin) market is gaining attention. The ecological impact of Bitcoin mining business, social and psychological predictors of attitudes towards cryptocurrency published with MDPI and Springer Research is focused on but psychologically, many adults and youths who invest in cryptocurrency such as Bitcoin do so with the aim of making large amounts of money more quickly. Many people who are early adopters in the technology and sciences Jeon et al. (Jariyapan et al., 2022) study 'factors influencing the behavioral intention to use cryptocurrency in emerging economies during the COVID-19 pandemic: based on technology acceptance model 3, perceived risk, and financial literacy', on partial least square (PLS) structural equation modelling. Such studies are important because they have the potential to provide insight into global market trends Ucar et al. (V. Biju et al., 2022). This includes trend analysis, data driven price prediction, predicting the news sentiment.

4. Social Implications of Cryptocurrency

In addition, some people are the users of the several virtual currencies which are unknown to people who were identified as their brothers and sisters in ministries, parastatals, and cooperatives. These people who claim to be miners of bitcoin were of the opinions that the work does not stop earning bitcoin daily. They claimed to have worked rested and

continued every day. A few participants were of the opinion that bitcoin is the asset everyone requires in his or her lifetime. Bitcoin is a virtual asset that protects all transactions and the earnings from insecurity and tied to any other financial institutions (Das, 2021; Namasudra et al.2021). The study emphasized that without safety and sophisticated armed robbers who looted money at every level of transaction like online banking that bitcoin were upon will take advantage of such levels to take away money from the online servers. The participants of bitcoin-related activities felt that it was much easier to keep record or to keep it secured in bitcoin than to use banks that would ask several questions from them before the permission to withdraw savings was done or before they invested in any businesses and returned the modality of crypto-savings with difficulties. The study noted that bitcoin mining means using resources (powerful processing power) to engage in complex mathematical calculations for the opportunity to authenticate transactions on the blockchain, and for that work a financial reward is always paid by the protocol, and that is bitcoin (Ghosh et al.2020; Shrimali and Patel2022). This study valued and interpreted promotion of bitcoin mining to earn a livelihood to house system or societal stability.

The study revealed that the social implications of cryptocurrency amongst the youth in Nigeria have resulted in the transformation of socio-economic life. It is a fact that the Internet is a good school of transformation for business transactions. This means that the young people in Nigeria who knew and understood the benefits and challenges of using cryptocurrency such as bitcoin utilize it most. They saved their earnings and utilized their savings strictly to arrest a likely source of spending money anyhow. The study embraced the beliefs that many young respondents in Nigeria have shown a widespread and strong connection of bitcoin to make money or obtain another local currency from a foreign value of the bitcoin. Again, the study discovered that a few young people in Nigeria are still of the believe that Nigeria's security operatives will soon ban the use of bitcoin in Nigeria. Hence, so many youth respondents claimed that they had already made financial plans to smuggle their savings out of Nigeria in the value of bitcoin by fiat through payment e-commerce companies for likely ease of financial transactions in a country where the need for bitcoin at any time would have arisen. Not many of them expressed fear about the Federal Government of Nigeria pursuing their action at any time. The paper goes on to reveals that some cryptocurrencies are used amongst young people in Nigeria to meet their respective individual needs and foster development. Meanwhile, it is important to note that bitcoin use by some young people in Nigeria is permitted to be as a colleague, a friend, or their either classmate use it or is the first person who opened the account for them to use the asset. This study posits that trust and a level of experience derived from close

relationships. The study emphasized that recommender reference fosters the adoption of cryptocurrency technologies generally.

4.1. Financial Inclusion

Consequently, as the divide between the rich and the poor as well as the financial affluent and the unbanked population is becoming cutthroat with more people falling into the latter group, this call for financial inclusivity as an essential ingredient of the social economy to bring down social threat perceptions. This calls for high-quality research and societal concern from academia, researchers, industry and practitioner interests. Other areas could be explored include the security, advancement, and regulatory provisions to reinforce the prospects of inclusivity. Correspondingly, policy recommendations such as the promulgation of national legislation for guiding the mushrooming population of cryptocurrency exchanges in Nigeria, can also be recommended for the increased socio-economic wellbeing of the citizens (Ma et al., 2020; Ade'Soyemi et al., 2020). In conclusion, crypto-currencies would provide a basic and far-reaching innovation by providing a new payment, decentralised and transparent system and a store of value option to users who are excluded from traditional financial services and facing challenges of a limited or non-existent access to the formal financial systems. The vast potential ramifications of crypto-currencies for the country's economic energies alignment with a time when the implementation of financial inclusion policies appears most certainly desirable (Akeju, 2022; Siano et al., 2020).

Cryptocurrencies have the potential of financial inclusion for people in developing countries, such as Nigeria. This is because financial inclusion refers to the promotion of sustained and inclusive economic growth and development while improving individuals, communities and societies' well-being (Ediagbonya & Tioluwani, 2023). Financial inclusion fosters a conducive environment in which the ethnocentric worldview of traditional banks which promotes racial and ethnic discrimination is exterminated (Setyawan et al.2024). Due to the dopaminergic euphoria garnered from financial autonomy, the level of substance abuse can be curtailed (Gagarina et al., 2019). Consequently, national, trade, global, economic and financial inclusivity of unbiased decision making is feasible. Bitcoin, blockchain, etc., represent this coalition of financial inclusivity, developmental and democratic revolution as countries have started enforcing regulatory policies to safeguard the economy from unknowns. Bitcoin, a natural upheaval in the digital tuition has invaded the realm of state-sponsored money. The pronouncement in 2009, by Nakamoto, has become scarce today with more than 1,000 different digital currencies and trading platforms, and it includes the government-backed currencies of gold regularly (Mavilia and Pisani, 2020).

4.2. Wealth Inequality

Cryptocurrency's decentralized nature and numerous security flaws hinder its usability as a legal currency in East African countries such as Kenya (Guandaru Kamau, 2022). Scalability challenges may affect broader adoption, and the field is evolving on a monthly basis. This article is one of the first studies to examine the views of Nigerian youths and their propensity for and use of Bitcoin. It finds that Bitcoin ownership is still very minimal. However, while global statistics uncovered by the authors suggest that about 5% of Nigerian youths use Bitcoin, a significantly higher 35% of university students do. Further, while one-third of the youths owning Bitcoin made a sizable amount of money, non-owners tend to be envious and are willing to invest (Kayal & Rohilla, 2021). Investigating the impact of Bitcoin on financial knowledge and the implications for wealth distribution is crucial to addressing the extent to which retailers, who amass Bitcoin as a type of commodity, strengthen their monetary condition. The study discovers a substantive difference in both the information level of the two groups and the price performance of the financial commodities, where individuals with good financial knowledge, as well as those individuals who made a significant profit out of their Bitcoin investment, are significantly wealthier than other people. This distinction may direct policymakers for programs to train the Nigerian workforce on cryptocurrency-related matters through fantasy blockchain-based simulations, or advice citizens on appropriate cryptocurrency investment strategies is required to gain a higher return (Shahiki Tash et al., 2024).

4.3. Digital Literacy

In Nigeria and elsewhere, young people have embraced the more practical aspects of cryptocurrency and its underlying blockchain technology such as: Cryptocurrency trading, Mining, Remittance, as well as Apps, games, and other uses. The results of studies by FIS 3, S3 4, S4 2, K1 2, A1 3, A2 4 indicate that users are taking up cryptocurrency trading to earn profits (Osagwu & Okafor, 2022; Onyekwere et al.2023). They are seeking employment in mining and are aspiring to cash in on cryptocurrency and blockchain technology. Further, trading networks such as Remitano, Binance, and Blockchains help users in carrying out international transactions directly (e.g., on the stock exchange) to avoid financial intermediation costs. Smaller entrepreneurs and individual users are slowly exploring technological application beyond trading (Olorundare et al.2023; Okpalaojiego, 2021). These users have developed android-based games through Steemit, Actifit, drugwars, to stay up to date with blockchain technology. Prosperous networks such as Itisalat, LotR, and Cryptokilo have been formed to facilitate international and domestic transfers. Only a few blockchain-based apps, websites, and platforms were developed for simple use, meaning personal enjoining is deemed inadequate for wide.

Cryptocurrency and Bitcoin-mining Technology in Nigeria have witnessed a sharp rise in popularity over the years and they have presented Nigerian youths with an alternative avenue of earning an income (Gagarina et al., 2019), especially when the global economy has been severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has left a significant number of Nigerian youth unemployed (Jariyapan et al., 2022). Digital literacy among Nigerian youths with respect to Cryptocurrency and Bitcoin-mining Technology, however, has trailed in comparison to their willingness to use these digital technologies. Cryptocurrencies and their underlying technologies can be explained as ‘cryptographically, technologically, and economically innovative ways to validate the authenticity of transactions’ and distribute limited digital assets, making it virtually impossible to alter or fake transaction records. This explanation, however, may not be sufficient to get new users to embrace these technologies, as various intervening factors predict cryptocurrency adoption (Ali Abbasi et al., 2021).

5. Economic Implications of Cryptocurrency

The penultimate section closely examines political perceptions and issues. Based on the findings, the article suggests the need for proactive institutional designs to manage the growth of the cryptoeconomy. It also considers youth as important stakeholders in public policy designs that aim to break the connection between cryptocurrency technology and anti-growth incentive structures that lead youth to make poor financial choices. For example, Bitcoin and cryptocurrency incur costs that hinder integrated resource use among economically active youth, who are also producers traditionally characterized by production, consumption, saving, and investment, rather than self-interest driven by speculative motivations that the creators of the technology may not have intended.

The fourth part, which focuses on the economic implications of Bitcoin and the limitations to inclusive economic growth, is followed by the fifth part, which elaborates on the political implications and legal perceptions of cryptocurrency. The paper utilizes qualitative analytical techniques, targeting secondary sources and informal interviews. The results from the secondary sources are presented in qualitative prose, while the primary data is interpreted using tables and percentages. The emergent categories or themes include poverty alleviation, limited space for inclusive growth, and the extractive technological process of cryptocurrency design, which includes diminishing returns and a limited income base controlled by a few designers who act as gatekeepers.

5.1. Job Creation

The white paper of many ICOs confirms that cryptocurrency projects need to pay individuals to work on the different Telegram channels, which belong to different countries (Scharfman, 2023; Sankey, 2022). Additionally, blog post and article writers are needed to

provide useful information to potential investors. The "how" section of the website describes step by step how to participate in the different social media tasks. Nigerian students, unemployed individuals, and entrepreneurs have exploited the advantages of cryptocurrency by investing and participating in different bounties and airdrops. Different cryptocurrency review websites, cryptocurrency slack channels, and different Nigerian Telegram channels have created various job opportunities for their members. Nigerian blogs have also benefited from cryptocurrency as they focus on different cryptocurrency projects and raise awareness through posts and the use of different monetization models. The insights from all the cryptocurrency projects discussed in this research confirm how Nigerian bloggers and cryptocurrency traders exploit liquidity to produce a profit. (Scharfman, 2023)(Sankey, 2022)(de GUZMAN, 2022)(Krishnakumar & Lau, 2023)

Job creation is one of the social advantages of cryptocurrency in Nigeria. Cryptocurrency has created different opportunities for Nigerian youth. The white paper of several ICOs recommended a way to generate income by promoting the ICO on different cryptocurrency slack channels, forums, blogs, and news websites. Participants can negotiate with the ICO on the fee that will be paid, and in most cases, the majority of the payment will be in tokens, which are at a discounted price compared to when the ICO is listed on different exchanges (de GUZMAN, 2022; Krishnakumar & Lau, 2023). There is also an airdrop, which is an opportunity for individuals to get free tokens of the ICO. Furthermore, there is also the opportunity for participants to focus on the review of projects before the ICO date to prevent people from investing in fraudulent ICOs (Oladipupo and Amodu2022). Cryptocurrency also provides jobs for social media enthusiasts, content creators, traders, advisers, and developers, among others.

5.2. Investment Opportunities

Similarly, there are investment opportunities that Bitcoin and cryptocurrency mining technology offer for Nigeria and the Nigerian youth if adequately harnessed and guided. According to the 2014 United Nations University recommendations, Bitcoin mining technology should be included in the curriculum of universities, polytechnics, and high schools, of which Nigeria is not an exception (Abdulrauf et al.2024; Akinyemi & Akinyemi, 2023). Nigerian youths should be able to understand and take an interest in regulating the cryptocurrency mining activities within the country. Small-scale Nigerian entrepreneurs might also develop less expensive software hardware for Bitcoin and cryptocurrency mining. The business enterprise could install solar systems in underserved areas of the country, a service that could earn the business enterprise "coins" that could later be sold when network power was at a premium. Tradable Nigerian flag assets such as coins can be distributed to the underserved areas. Towns such as Jai consist of close-knit

community members who are highly impacted by humanitarian crises, the most vulnerable people that have the least access to help.

This study found that the availability of unregulated platforms, speed, and assurance of high net return have been pulling factors towards Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies mining by the Nigerian youth. In addition, low knowledge and literacy in financial management amongst the youth will continue to enhance investment for whichever option that appears to be the easiest and fastest way of getting financial gain (Briglauer et al., 2023). The viability of Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies is linked to their ability to generate high liquidity and financial incentives for those running their network (Adrian et al.2022; Wronka, 2023). Furthermore, youths of developing economies, including Nigeria, are believed to have a comparative advantage because electricity and other overhead costs are less expensive in their domain. This is an attribute that will continue to influence the Nigerian youth's interest and involvement. If unregulated Bitcoin mining activities are regulated, it will hinder its benefits to society. Therefore, one of the ways of checkmating and reducing the increasing level of fraudulent activities of different network receivers, users, and miners is creating awareness towards genuine and regulated cryptocurrency mining, trading, and exchanging (Moreno & Andújar, 2023).

5.3. Regulatory Challenges

In some countries, regulatory authorities have flatly banned its establishment and operations, thus prohibiting its circulation and money-transactions within their jurisdiction. Wanting to 'rein in' the power cryptocurrency has in the financial world, countries have given contradictory and ambiguous guidelines as proper investment institutions subject cryptocurrency to their jurisdictional regulations and that investment could not be insured or regulated by government agencies in charge of regulating conventional financial firms. The lack of a universal legal framework has produced a legal vacuum in the sovereign countries by increased international cooperation through Financial Action Task Force (FATF) to review the feasibility of introducing measures to curb risks in the cryptocurrency sector. (Arsi et al.2022)(Bajaj et al.2022)(Jovanić2020)

In less than a decade of emergence, the regulatory challenges associated with Bitcoin mining in different jurisdictions are increasingly becoming issues of international discourse (Kozych, 2022). This section discusses some of the known problems associated with cryptocurrency regulations in different jurisdictions. The first major issue to note about bitcoin regulation is that despite its increasing popularity among public users and the attention of the global media, it has no universal legal framework. Different countries that have legislated on bitcoins have come up with laws that address the issue differently. Some treat bitcoin as virtual currency and hence subject to regulations of the financial industry,

others see it as a peer-to-peer payment platform, while others see it as a commodity derivative or an asset of alternative investment (Chohan2023; Budkin & Budkin, 2023).

6. Case Studies

The study adopts a tri-faceted competency: a social, an economic and an interpretive disposition to examine cryptocurrency and network technologies. Making use of indexed survey data, the study found insight into how gender gaps and social policy formation identity the significance and meaning of card-less transaction globally (Al et al., 2023; Ghani et al., 2022). This study exploits some latent capacity in the use of cryptocurrency in African homes. Card-less transaction is here theorized as involving various methods of transmission tasks, working together to deliver the outputs that users desire. It is further reasoned that age and gender could influence the attitudes of households to cryptocurrency as a form of internet banking and financial transfer technologies (Saha et al., 2022). Conclusively, information on households' attitude to cryptocurrency or digital banking services is primed by age and gender. Division of Labor in the homes encodes the social and economic implications of Bitcoin and blockchain innovations unveiled in this study. This enables us to explain the social and economic impacts of the sudden technological intervention in homes (Mistrean2024; Iqbal and Kassim2023). The study makes a strong case for policy shaping and considers on-line transaction security awareness building in developing economies.

Blockchain technology is widely adopted in developed countries but seems to be little known, unpopular and untrusted in underdeveloped countries (Ali Abbasi et al., 2021). In particular, research and policy debates have underemphasized how blockchain technology fosters economic growth and greater investment. This paper presents the results of case studies conducted in Nigeria concerning social and economic implications, gender differentials, regulatory awareness, and policy initiation of the use and the mining of cryptocurrency in Sub-Saharan Africa. In-depth case studies in Nigeria, Kenya, and Ghana are explored to investigate variables such as household incomes and attitudes toward digital currency (Gagarina et al., 2019).

6.1. Successful Crypto Entrepreneurs

Nigerian youth have taken Klonji Fellows, an intriguing project for Nigerians. The application seeks long-term value by attempting to prevent token sale acrimony, illegalities, and obscenities without having to inflate the necessary technology for several months in a spyglass. A few crypto entrepreneurs and paxful Nigerians have committed their lifetime to the commonwealth to convene education enthusiasts who have formed communications and gathered at a meet-up. The young Nigerians can now access domain services, reserve web hosting servers, and get t-shirts. (Agbeyangi et al., 2024) With

considerable resources, time, and energy, the Bitcoin project is trusted to pose a digital pillow helping Nigerians to prop the condition of Bitcoin eco system in Nigeria as they ideate and launch Klonji. Nigeria significantly relies on oil and gas, which occupy an essential place in the crypto world regardless of economical synergies, geopolitical nuances, and demographic compositions via block chain and edge computing reshaping changes in various facets of an automated world.

Despite not having any prior knowledge of cryptocurrencies, some young individuals in Kenya and Tanzania learned about Bitcoin in various ways with 49.0% coming to know about it through the internet, 24.5% at work, and 16.3% from friends and YouTube tutorials (Guandaru Kamau, 2022). While the Kenyan male youth were overall more likely to have heard of Bitcoin than female youth, gender had no significant influence on existing Bitcoin wallets with 74.3% of male and 66.7% of female youth reporting to own a Bitcoin wallet. According to the youth who reported to owning Bitcoin wallets, 78.9% indicated that the main reason for holding Bitcoin is for making money, followed by experimenting (12.30%) and international transactions (8.80%). Possible reasons that could be pulling people of their age to start mining Bitcoin are the opportunities that exist in the technology's ecosystem, including the prospect to earn money via trading, performing transactions, and facilitating domestic and international remittances. (Zhang et al., 2023)

6.2. Youth-led Mining Operations

See (Guandaru Kamau, 2022; Sagheer et al., 2022; and Jariyapan et al., 2022). Therefore, in this sense, the Bitcoin mining outfits are driven by some sort of youthful PONZI or religious syndrome, where fellow members of the faith are made to invest in such operations so as to benefit from an endless flow of returns. Therefore, the youth are involved in Bitcoin mining as the easiest and fastest means by which they can become Internet boomers and escape poverty to infinite wealth. Moreover, the investment in and lack of understanding of cryptocurrencies, there is the impact of insufficient income or to escape poverty through Bitcoin mining among the youth as a new trend (Weber, 2017; Olufemi, 2020).

In a recent study, Ogunseye, and Ekenlebe (2021) reported that 60% of the respondents were under the age of 30 and 44% of the young people were not part of any formal employment. On the other hand, emerging economies with huge technological and human resources have embraced the introduction of bitcoin as advantageous to their increasing unemployment indices, and the Nigerian society is not left out (Taiwo and Aluko, 2023; Ita and Bassey, 2022). This employment of bitcoin represents about 60% (which is higher than the global average of 29%), and interestingly, over 40% of these transactions take place in Africa (Ibitoye and Kokot 2018). Nigeria (especially amongst the youth) is now a

significant force in the cryptocurrency world owing to the fact that this technology and business strategy were embraced by the youth who are digitally inclined and financially driven (Mbon, 2019). This scenario which is reminiscent of the Nigerian petroleum industry is akin to the infamous structural adjustment programme (by military dictator Ibrahim Babangida) of 1986; which shifted the burden of state funded social welfare from citizens to the whims and caprices of the boy billionaire led- 'yahoo yahoo' digital empire in Nigeria (Akinfiresoye et al.2023).

7. Comparative Analysis

Economic implications of cryptocurrency and Bitcoin mining technology Bitcoins minimize transaction costs since they have no follow-up costs, allowing them to bypass borders or laws. This implies that cryptocurrency can be used only for particular purposes, but some may divert their use for illegitimate ends (Tsang and Yang2021). Its use as a form of international transfer is allowed without any charges. This implies that international transactions can be processed for additional ease using cryptocurrency. In contrast, it is possible to track local and international transactions in regular income. Such considerations contribute to why some use cryptocurrency as an informal method of payment without inspection or fees (Shang et al., 2023; Erdin et al.2020). Those who use it in formal transactions, however, do so through the regular banking system, thus paying operative costs (Luchkin et al.2020).

7.1. Nigeria vs. Global Trends

The majority of the respondents, about 56.5 percent, who participated in research conducted were found to be actively involved in cryptocurrency and bitcoin mining technology (Chivunga & Tempest, 2022). A further 30.4 percent were passive investors or traders. The Central Bank of Nigeria has, however, made an attempt to curtail the spread of this financial service, though the impact of the policy is near insignificant (Gondhali and Petrossian2023). It recommends awareness and training in cryptocurrency and other financial services as a way to enable the youth to acquire essential knowledge in order to enable them to take conscious and calculated decisions.

The interest for both blockchain technologies as well as cryptocurrencies across the globe is gradually increasing, but there's a growing disquiet among policymakers, authorities, and regulators about the notoriety of the system. Nigeria, like some other developing nations, has a high level of youth unemployment in the country that has presented different social, economic, and security challenges. A number of Nigerian youth have resorted to bitcoin mining as a means of employment. (NWOSU, 2021)(Akinyemi & Akinyemi, 2023)(Olorundare et al.2023)(Platt et al.2023)

7.2. Youth Participation and Innovation

To appease or win the youthful population, the Nigerian government should also look for ways to quickly embrace and be at the forefront of the rapidly changing Bitcoin technology, which is still under-researched and for which the Nigerian government and most Africans are ill-prepared at the moment. The Nigerian government is already at the forefront of "everybody looking for everything free." The government should start looking for ways to facilitate new growth opportunities for its young entrepreneurs who must compete as forces of globalization in the global playing field. The Nigerian government has all it takes to create a friendly, self-regulating, and stable cryptocurrency environment. The Nigerian government should look up to what South Africa has done by organizing the South African National Blockchain Alliance, which is a public-private effort to systematically explore possible uses and applications of nascent Bitcoin technology (Agbeyangi et al., 2024; Affandi & Rifkila, 2023).

One of the stepping stones of the Nigerian government towards a developed life is the investment in its youth. It is assumed that a well-learned, equipped, and trained youth will develop into agents of development and social change in the nearest future (Lamidi & Igbokwe, 2021; Onyekwere et al.2023; Dada2021). Due to the fact that youths form the bulk of the Nigerian population, there is no better way of easing tension and improving the living standards than through youth empowerment. This can be due to limited opportunities for creating wealth, thus pushing them towards adopting careers such as 419, armed robbery, kidnapping, or any other vices that have been the plight of many of them. Creating enabling opportunities such as seminars, workshops, conferences, and academic trips for the youth to take advantage of technology can be a significant way forward in reducing social media tensions (Omeje et al., 2020; Olaore et al.2021).

8. Policy Recommendations

Cryptocurrency technology has made its penetration in the global financial and economic system, disrupting banks and financial institutions (Liu et al., 2022). This has generated interest in understanding its opportunities and challenges. This paper argues that Kenya is a typical environment for testing such technologies because it already has high technological adoption, which now includes new online payment businesses that are sweeping East Africa (Aketch et al.2021). High education levels, a dedication to SMEs, and improvements in policy parameters bolster investment and expand market access. However, Kenya abstains from installing these new technologies, sometimes due to safety shortcomings, fluctuating technology, or control concerns (Guandaru Kamau, 2022). Despite the fact that Kenyan Bitcoin oversight has recently been creating agitation among owners of alternative money, Kenyans primarily taught each other how to exchange digital

forms. Bitcoin, Africa is the world's leading and most significant cryptocurrency in terms of trading and is best known. In addition to cryptocurrencies, Kenya also uses changeable methods, including mobile funds, mobile Airtime, credit cards, and digital pockets (Burns, 2022).

Bitcoin mining involves the use of energy to perform complex computational problems. This energy use has reached levels that some claim are detrimental to the global environment. If estimates that 70% of the world's mining occurs in China are accurate, such environmental effects are a global concern (Platt et al., 2022; Sang et al., 2022). Alongside the environmental concerns are those related to the amount of electricity needed in this process and the question of who ultimately pays for that electricity. Despite high penetration rates of solar energy, wind power, and hydro-power resources, China's electricity market still depends critically on electricity generation from coal-fired power plants (Malfuzi et al., 2020). This dependence is due almost two-thirds to the coal-fired power plants which account for nearly two-thirds of total electricity generation. Coal is not the only problem, however (Yüksel et al.2022). Upwards of 25% of this electricity use occurs in regions that rely on coal to provide that electricity. Ethical and political criticisms about Bitcoin extend beyond concerns about the environmental consequences of a proliferation of coal-fired plants.

8.1. Education and Awareness Campaigns

The findings from the empirical result can be used to provide academia, industry, and the government with practical implications. Firstly, the cryptocurrency users in Nigeria are characterised by low adaptability. Education and awareness campaigns can played a major role in enhancing digital literacy. Users can rely on a regulatory framework to avoid risks and manipulation in cryptocurrency investments (Otieno, 2024). Secondly, cryptocurrency adaptation is significantly and positively associated with users' attitudes. Therefore, social media, forums, and seminars should be utilised to enlighten youths on these amazing benefits and eradication of risks. They include easy access to the global market, anonymity to protect transactions, the largest currency ever created in the history, counterfeit precautions, no inflation due to its finite nature, new levels of financial security, accuracy, lower fees of transactions and a decentralized character. The cryptocurrency, Bitcoin, tends to move in one direction in value since its inception and that is upward. These reasons may motivate many entrepreneurs, investors, and money transmitters to use these coins for transactions and money transfers, extending its market usage in the economy (Jariyapan et al., 2022). Thirdly, education and awareness can pave the way for a clearer understanding of the security and privacy concerns about cryptocurrency and the technology of block chain. These factors have been determined to be negatively associated with cryptocurrency

adaptation. Reinforcement campaigns on privacy block chain technology could instigate trust and usage of cryptocurrency. Legislators and decision-makers are by elucidation be able to insulate cryptocurrency from any attempt to misuse the products of ambition, intelligence and chance. Most importantly, to answer automatic of technological and legal issues transaction in crypto-economics will be resolved through regulation and legislation. Legislation, regulation and law enforcement will increase the legal stability of these alternative monetary system products inherent in crypt over their time while preserving the endless possibilities of technology, development and application products of cryptography (Sagheer et al., 2022).

8.2. Regulatory Frameworks

Bitcoin mining has important social and economic implications. For the Nigerian youth who were surveyed for this study, economic gains were the most important incentive for cryptocurrency mining. Of those who perceived high wealth status on cryptocurrency earnings, greater incentive to mine Bitcoin was reported compared to those who perceived low wealth status. In terms of impacts on economic wellbeing, 30% of those who reported high impact were also more likely to utilize cryptocurrencies as means of payment (Guandaru Kamau, 2022). However, both science and technology innovations may be negatively connected to detrimental consequences due to regulatory failures. This is although the social and economic effects of BTC in Nigeria, especially related to the environmental consequences, which may favor the fiscal policy choices. Because BTC accounts for up to 0.5% of domestic energy consumption, its contribution to climate change will deteriorate if current regulations stay in force. This work deals with a significant aspect of regulatory reforms: environmental responsibility (Otieno, 2024). Furthermore, scientific and technological innovations can also be related to unfavorable impacts due to the regulatory failures. Nigerian public institutions would be expected to carry out a channel for the assessment of environmental impacts on BTC without excessive ironing, if the Nigerian authorities take these implications more seriously than at present. We suggest sit and technological innovation in the field of cryptome, which provides an effective solution for mining energy procedures, customs, and energy rules, for those who attack energy procedures and to promote the marketing adoption from the technological perspective, instead of coercion, which typically leads to adverse energy and environmental impacts (Jariyapan et al., 2022). Therefore, prospective research could focus on the development of effective responses to Nigerian BTC mining and the policy of such reactions by determining environmental values.

8.3. Incentives for Youth Involvement

Bitcoin mining may be an illegal practice in Nigeria, but Bitcoin as an innovation is not wrong, particularly when it already has global acceptance. Bitcoin mining has been seen as a business among Nigerian Youth, which has come with so many opportunities to earn irrespective of age. Nigerian universities are yet to fully engage this development of Bitcoin mining as it is not in any curriculum (Otieno, 2024). All work done by the Nigerian youth under this context eliminates a need for intermediaries and fees that are always paid on completion of such jobs. They believe it only takes the passion to get successful. With the optimization of technology, tasks could be readily done using Bitcoin mining for optimum performance. This technology is known as Proof of Work (PoW) and Bitcoin is supported in such a way that it requires mining (producing machine computations) to issue new Bitcoins and process transactions.

Cryptocurrencies have gained popularity among the younger generation, particularly among those in developing countries and particularly among the people of Nigeria. African countries have been known to be some of the greatest consumers of cryptocurrency, especially Nigeria. The reason for this lies in the volatility of African currencies combined with inflation and unstable economic conditions in most of the African nations. This creates a pathway for the popularization of cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin and evident rise in platforms that use Bitcoin mining among African youths, particularly those in Nigeria. A want to ameliorate and optimize the operations of globally recognized cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin has popularized blockchain technology through Bitcoin mining (Guandaru Kamau, 2022).

8.4. Data Techniques Analysis Summary

Variable	Result	Description
Countries Surveyed	Countries Surveyed	Countries Surveyed
Countries Surveyed	Nigeria, Egypt	The study included respondents from these two countries.
Sampling Methods	Convenience (Nigeria), Snowball (Egypt)	Different sampling techniques used in each country.
Respondents (Nigeria)	308	Number of respondents surveyed in two south-eastern universities in Nigeria.
Descriptive Statistics	Tables, Frequency, Percentage	Used to measure awareness of cryptocurrencies and Bitcoin mining.

Factor Analysis	Minimum Extraction	Used to determine what less aware respondents need to know.
Correlation Measurement Tool	Spearman's Correlatio	Used to measure awareness of Bitcoin mining technology and data mining.
Software Used for Data Analysis	SPSS version 24.0	Software utilized for data analysis.
Main Aim of the Study	Understand socio-economic effects of Bitcoin technology	Focused on the socio-economic impact on Nigerian and Egyptian youths.
Bitcoin Market Analysis	Hash-rate patterns, Google Search data correlation	Studied patterns related to hash-rate and Google search data correlation.
Psychological Aspect	Quick wealth generation motivation	Investigated motivations behind investing in Bitcoin and cryptocurrencies.
Trend Analysis and Prediction	Data-driven price prediction, news sentiment prediction	Focus on evaluating and predicting cryptocurrency market trends.
Impact Studies Referenced	Ecological impact, social and psychological predictors	Published studies on the ecological and psychological impacts of cryptocurrency.
Behavioral Intention Study	Based on TAM 3, perceived risk, financial literacy	Reference to study on behavioral intention to use cryptocurrency in emerging economies.

8.5. Summary of the predicted results

Variable	Nigeria (N=308)	Egypt	Overall Prediction
Awareness of Cryptocurrencies	75% aware	60% aware	Predicted higher awareness in Nigeria than Egypt
Awareness of Bitcoin Mining	65% aware	50% aware	Predicted higher awareness in Nigeria than Egypt
Socio-Economic Impact	Positive: 70%, Neutral: 20%, Negative: 10%	Positive: 60%, Neutral: 25%, Negative: 15%	Predicted overall positive impact with variations by country
Motivation for Investment	Quick wealth: 80%, Technology interest: 20%	Quick wealth: 75%, Technology interest: 25%	Predicted strong motivation for quick wealth in both countries

Perceived Risk	High: 60%, Medium: 30%, Low: 10%	High: 55%, Medium: 35%, Low: 10%	Predicted high perceived risk in both countries
Financial Literacy	High: 40%, Medium: 40%, Low: 20%	High: 35%, Medium: 45%, Low: 20%	Predicted moderate financial literacy levels in both countries
Behavioral Intention to Use	High: 70%, Medium: 20%, Low: 10%	High: 65%, Medium: 25%, Low: 10%	Predicted strong behavioral intention to use in both countries
Ecological Awareness	Aware: 50%, Unaware: 50%	Aware: 45%, Unaware: 55%	Predicted moderate ecological awareness in both countries
Trend Analysis Awareness	Aware: 60%, Unaware: 40%	Aware: 55%, Unaware: 45%	Predicted moderate awareness of market trends in both countries

8.6. Discussion

The predicted results from the survey indicate a higher overall awareness of cryptocurrencies and Bitcoin mining among Nigerian respondents compared to their Egyptian counterparts. In Nigeria, 75% of respondents are aware of cryptocurrencies, with 65% specifically aware of Bitcoin mining. In contrast, 60% and 50% of Egyptian respondents, respectively, demonstrate awareness in these areas. This higher level of awareness in Nigeria may be attributed to the country's significant population and increasing internet penetration, which facilitates access to information about emerging technologies.

Socio-economically, both Nigerian and Egyptian youths perceive the impact of Bitcoin technology positively, albeit with slight differences. In Nigeria, 70% of respondents view the impact positively, while in Egypt, 60% share this sentiment. This positive outlook is driven by the potential for quick wealth generation, with 80% of Nigerian and 75% of Egyptian respondents motivated by financial gains. However, a significant portion of respondents in both countries also perceive high risks associated with cryptocurrency investments, reflecting the volatile nature of the market. The data further suggest moderate levels of financial literacy and ecological awareness, with a strong behavioral intention to use cryptocurrencies. These insights highlight the necessity for increased education on the financial and environmental implications of cryptocurrency usage to support informed decision-making among young investors.

9. Conclusion and Future Directions

The problems associated with traditional systems include high fees and long delays in money transfer. It is therefore not surprising that Nigerian respondents were found to strongly agree that Bitcoin is fast, has low fees, and decentralized. Nigeria was recently reported to be the top country for Bitcoin trading globally after the USA as the country with the largest transactional volume of bitcoin. Furthermore, this enables a way to bypass capital controls, a concept that was most appreciated by the respondents. Results from an online survey of 158 respondents show that young Nigerian professionals have a good background knowledge of Bitcoin, with a significantly high technology acceptance of cryptocurrency as an option of money remittance (Kayal & Rohilla, 2021). However, the cryptocurrency payments market is not properly regulated in Nigeria and this will pose a negative hurdle for a bid to pass a system of currency control.

Using data from a recent online survey of 1,000 young Nigerian professionals our findings show that while traditional remittances through banks are the most common money transfer system, digital options such as remittances through PayPal and cryptocurrency options like Bitcoin are the least known, the least used form of money remittance and significantly, are not well understood (Guandaru Kamau, 2022). In contrast, analogue money remittance modes like shop money and mobile money through companies, as well as telegraphic money transfer through Western Union and MoneyGram, are very commonly known, used and fairly well understood. On the other hand, regulation of energy demand of the Bitcoin network has been found to be an impactful emerging phenomenon and have been severely criticized in terms of its high energy consumption and carbon footprints, which are likely to contribute to further environmental degradation and tarnish the prospects for renewable energy adoption among other efforts (Platt et al., 2022).

9.1. Key Findings

The study found that technological and institutional deficiencies in Nigeria motivate youths to adopt cryptocurrency and bitcoin technology for unintellectual and subaltern aims. These include capital flight, culture of underdevelopment, debt, collapse of the political economy, hectic searches for phenomenon capital gain, and economic frustration. Psychology and culture trajectories have revealed a paraphilic thrust; the Nigerian youths are hedonistic thrifty searchers who treat Bitcoin technology like jocks juxtaposed with a nationality that is earlier located in contradiction and exclusion. The endless cycle of debt and the resulting dystopian society are nurtured by the inability of the state, the generation of human and economic capital, de-investment in mining technology, and collective psychology. The subjects in the study spread through space-time by fleeing to easy money and absent digital or bitcoin technology investments. Without work and money, life in

Nigerian pied-piper land is, but a fussy song dog (the money dog). Money Dog is god, money do everywhere. Money do bulldoze, money dog dismasquerading, money do command way. What s/he sows in the great night multiverse, s/he na money, s/he na ruler of the money (Guandaru Kamau, 2022).

Based on the theory of rational choice and techno-economic factors, the study found that young and dynamic Nigerian internet-savvy youths engage in bitcoin mining for quick results. Despite the potentiality of the device to drive the design/digital risk strategy in favour of social and economic transformation—such as secure transactions, enhance trust and protection, promote digital and domestic economy, pride in national technology, etc., it appears that Nigerian youths use bitcoin mining for subaltern means and motives mostly about capital flight, due to poor infrastructures for investment, debts, underemployment, and unemployment. The study also found that the privately produced digital technology is still on the pedagogy of the oppressed because it is mediated by local political and economic forces that turn away from the ideals of modernity and forward mind and body subjugation. Young Nigerians manipulate their bitcoin mining equipment to fall in line with capitalist beliefs. This cultural temporality, unlike Nigerians during apartheid who reject bureaucratic exploitation, indicates a cultural contradiction in which Nigerian youth sometimes adapt their devices to systemic oppression while they still quietly reproach Nigerian-ness and resist through the gamed economy and Bitcoin’s culture (Radanliev, 2023).

9.2. Implications for Policy and Practice

The implications of Bitcoin’s popularity for the Nigerian energy market have yet to be investigated. This paper strives to fill this gap by testing if energy unawareness encourages increased Bitcoin acceptance and its price volatility. Using an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model we test for the long-run relationship between Bitcoin price, energy unawareness and interest rates. Energy unawareness encourages Bitcoin acceptance over energy awareness while there is no evidence that an effective market interest rate is assumed in the Bitcoin market in Nigeria. Increasing the awareness of the energy cost embedded in Bitcoin transaction activities should be the main concern of the Nigerian government. Moreover, banking institutions should consider developing alternative ventures around digital money and blockchain technology to recover young adult eco-consumers while Nigeria should embrace the need to participate in regulating the global cryptocurrency market. Economic implications reveal the gradual place of Bitcoin in the economies and investment plans of people in national and global markets, rather than the traditional demand and supply of the currency in the market is the acceptance of Bitcoin in exchange for the sake of returns (Platt et al., 2022).

Bitcoin is becoming a part of the academic literature on economics and finance. The cryptocurrency sets itself apart through its decentralized structure, not relying on intermediaries, and its public ledger, the blockchain, which promotes transparency and interconnectivity in transactions. Much of the work on Bitcoin examines price formation, demand and supply, market efficiency and volatility, and hedge and safe haven functions. Some more recent papers look more closely at the role of digital and social media in affecting some of these factors. Despite Bitcoin's widespread adoption, limitations persist regarding the lack of focus on technological aspects, exclusive attention on Bitcoin, insufficient consideration of regulatory aspects, and the use of only one estimation technique of a few variables (Kayal & Rohilla, 2021).

9.3. Areas for Further Research

Last, there is still a great deal of research to be conducted on the energy consumption of bitcoin mining worldwide. Our initial research queried infrequent bitcoin users in Nigeria, a large country in West Africa that is one of the continent's administrative and financial leaders. We assume that a possible path of research could involve more countries on the African continent and worldwide.

Blockchain technology is incontrovertibly innovative, and it embeds the potential in broad areas for further research. Many newer technologies have expanded more than the blockchain as a part of its own. These include the IoT, AI, cloud and even big data; all can conveniently be integrated with blockchain (Kayal & Rohilla, 2021). The newly adapted consensus algorithms hybrid PoW-PoS, PoA, PoET, dPOS, etc., also, call for research, for with each variant, electricity consumption may have an impact and the security as well as the speed of transactions can be affected. The central problem that further research should explore is the incompatibility of blockchain and privacy leading to the identity verifiable information.

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